

PECULARITIES OF APHORISMS DESCRIBING HAPPINESS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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This article describes the concept of happiness in the field of aphorisms in English language including information on the way how people speaking this language determine happiness and their attitude towards achieving it, which constitutes great value of information in the field of linguocultural studies.

Aphorisms as being the statements of prominent people on certain social and domestic issues are always aimed at putting forward basic ideas on topical issues of society [Cherkashina, 2016]. Humanity in its development process by acquiring life experience and knowledge collected and formed certain ideas on these topics, which in turn are displayed with the help of language forming certain concepts.

It has always been that people who speak different languages can have similar conceptual pictures of the world under certain conditions, while people who speak the same language can have completely different views. Consequently, in the conceptual picture of the world, the universal, national and personal interact, and the system of socially typical positions, relations, assessments find a symbolic reflection in the system of the national language and takes part in the construction of the linguistic picture of the world.[Nalichnikova, 2016].

Happiness has always in different cultures and in different eras of human development had different definitions and concepts, which naturally depend directly on the worldview of people. For example, according to Lysenko for a person in a primitive society up to the middle Ages, happiness was considered in a narrow circle of physical needs satisfaction, taking into account hunger, epidemics and diseases of then tormenting people. While in Ancient Antique culture, owing to the Ancient Renaissance the great philosophers Aristotle, Dionysus, Socrates and others already had formed more abstract concepts about happiness and its representation in the world. In ancient Greece, a fortune and religion were considered as happiness, i.e. the fate of a person under the protection of gods. The founder of ethics as a science, Aristotle, associated happiness with the state of the soul, when a virtuous life brings a person pleasure and moral satisfaction, the possession of various benefits. With the gradual development of the world, humanity completely changes its concept of happiness; it already ceases to be something between satisfying hunger and the desire to live in wealth. In the era of Wars, for example, life in peace and outside of wars became the main element of the presentation of happiness, taking into account all the disasters that have plagued people's lives in connection with the battles. However, by the era of the Renaissance, more extensive concepts of happiness appear, taking into account the improvement made in the quality of life and other factors.[Lysenko, 2016]

In the twentieth century, according to the happiness in the novel of the American writer Francis Scott Fitzgerald "The Great Gatsby" is displayed not in the light of money, wealth and fame, but rather on something more mundane in the spirit of friendship, love and loyalty. Steadily, people began to consider happiness not as a material value, but more in a spiritual state. While in Soviet Union countries, the topic of freedom and freedom of speech predominates in the works of

many Soviet writers of that time M.Yu.Bulgakov "The Master and Margarita", B.L.Pasternak "Doctor Zhivago" displaying ideas on freedom from censorship as being determinative point of happiness.

Aphorisms, being a descriptive element of language and linguistic culture as a whole, most reflect precisely such issues of society and carry valuable information about the culture of a particular language. For a more accurate contrastive analysis, let us analyze aphorisms describing happiness in English language.

If we consider the concept of happiness in the English language in the light of aphorisms, based on the following aphorisms describing happiness then we can say that English culture mainly emphasizes that happiness is closely connected not with the past or the future, but with the present.

"The chief part of a person's happiness consists of pleasure."

Thomas More [Matveev, 2019]

«Мы не знаем, что будет завтра; наше дело — быть счастливыми сегодня.»

Сидней Смит [Matveev, 2012]

"It is not how much we have, but how much we enjoy, that makes happiness"

Charles Spurgeon. [Matveev, 2012]

«The moments of happiness we enjoy take us by surprise. It is not that we seize them, but that they seize us.»

Ashley Montagu [Matveev, 2012]

"Happiness cannot be traveled to, owned, earned, worn or consumed. Happiness is the spiritual experience of living every minute with love, grace, and gratitude."

Denis Waitley [Matveev, 2012]

In these aphorisms concept of happiness directly related with pleasure, enjoyment and not considered in material items but rather on the inner peace and joy. Consequently, English aphorisms describing happiness mainly encourage people to live in the present and not put off life until later. One possible reason for this is perhaps the pragmatism of the European people and their easy attitude of to life at all.

As were mentioned above happiness has always had different interpretation over the period of its development even in English culture therefore for example in the period of development of dystopia genre in English literature (XVI century) which is emphasized in striving for creating ideal human world and getting joy from it, which is definitely had impact on the aphorisms of that period making the happiness and pleasure as equal concepts.

«The chief part of a person's happiness consists of pleasure.»

Thomas More

Moreover, majority of aphorisms still concentrated on the idea that each individuals responsible for he/her own happiness:

"Happiness is wanting what you get. If you have health, you probably will be happy, and if you have health and happiness, you have all the wealth you need, even if it is not all you want."

[unknown author]

Consequently, in the process of analyzing aphorisms describing happiness in English language, it can be concluded that despite differences in their determination of happiness we can nevertheless say that the most similar points of the aphorisms describing happiness in this

culture is considered to be based on not in material values, but rather in spiritual state and health.

References:

1. E.A. Cherkashina. The concept of Happiness in the Russian language
2. Лысенко.М.А. Концепт счастье и его метафорическое преломление. Маг. Диссертация. Екатеринбург.2016
3. S.Matveev. English aphorisms. Saint Petesburg.2012
4. I.Nalichnikova. Aphorisms as genre, minor text and universal statement.article.2016
5. <https://ktonanovenkogo.ru/voprosy-i-otvety/aforizmy-chto-ehto-takoe.html>
9. <https://www.egreenway.com/virtues/happiness.htm>
10. <https://www.egreenway.com/virtues/happiness.htm>
11. <https://www.egreenway.com/virtues/happiness.htm>
12. Geary.J. The World in a Phrase: A Brief History of the Aphorism.2005
13. Gopnik.A.Brevity, Soul, Wit: The art of the aphorism.2019
14. Комарова З. И. Методология, метод, методика и технология научных исследований в лингвистике: учебное пособие. – Екатеринбург: Изд-во УрФУ, 2012.